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**Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements of MSc in
Computer Engineering (Artificial Intelligence and Robotics)**

Brain Age Prediction Using a Brain Multi-atlas-based Ensemble Deep Regression Method

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Chapter 1

General Background

1-1 Introduction

The brain is a complex body organ that holds a number of main roles to manage the human consciousness and activities.

Brain disorders include brain tumors, trauma, cerebrovascular diseases, autoimmune brain diseases, neurodegenerative diseases and mental disorders. Their variety and high rates make people of different regions, ages, genders and state of education and income susceptible to be affected by these brain disorders. Neurological disorders in specific are considered in the world of medicine to be the hardest to diagnose, manage, monitor and treat due to the brain and in general the nervous system complexity (Siuly and Zhang, 2016). Such disorders cause brain atrophy which accelerates the ageing of the brain signaled by the degeneration of brain cell and molecules (Wrigglesworth *et al.*, 2021). Different medical brain images are considered as the main techniques to diagnose and monitor the brain pathology through the usage of artificial intelligence models to overcome different challenges. Artificial intelligence plays the main role in different techniques used for the medical imaging analysis, including images pre-processing, image processing, model building and features analysis (Cenek *et al.*, 2018). Some techniques aim for solving classification problems such as distributing the images into categories for disease diagnosis, while others aim for solving regression problems such as studying the relationship between different variables or predicting a content-based variable as the brain age... etc.

1-2 Thesis Statement

Neurodegenerative and psychiatric diseases share similar pathophysiology (Wingo *et al.*, 2022) that cause different abnormal changes in the brain structure and functionality where, consequently, the gap between predicted age and chronological age grows. As a result, the estimated brain age may be a direct feature used in estimating patients' stage of brain related diseases and their corresponding diagnosis, prognosis and treatment, and it can be used in some cases to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving brain health, such as cognitive training programs or medications, in addition to being a direct indicator of a person's general lifestyle to be classified of being healthy or not (Baecker *et al.*, 2021). Neuroimaging techniques are the main techniques used for detecting the changes occurring in the brain structure. As for the morphological changes derived from neuroimaging techniques directly related to the brain aging, they include the grey matter changes and white matter changes. Among different changes including volume loss, widening and ventriculomegaly, morphological and pathologic changes can be evaluated using MRI, DTI and CT scans, whereas brain connectivity is analyzed through fMRI scans through the evaluation of white matter track (Ota and Shah, 2022). Functional connectivity derived from fMRI scans can help in the analysis of the brain functional organization and learning informative brain features, as it can principally be used as a capable measure for the prediction of brain age. Deep learning models are considered to be reliable models for integrating the medical images and functional connectivity data to achieve different analysis objectives such as brain age prediction (Li, Satterthwaite and Fan, 2018a). Among different deep models, GCN models were considered to be the most effective in fMRI analysis due to their ability to use spatial features between neighboring nodes for connectivity-based convolution (Wang, Li and Hu, 2021). Region of interest selection of fMRI data to construct the model network population is effective for calculating the connectivity correlations (Sohn *et al.*, 2015). Accordingly, we are concerned about the effectiveness of using connectivity-based GCN model for brain age prediction using fMRI scans.

1-3 Thesis Challenges

1- fMRI are complicated gigantic data structures that contain a lot of noisy data described using different types of CIFTI files each containing different information concerning the subject scan.

2- Subjects' describing graphs can be constructed with different strategies, which makes it more complicated to decide the best suitable construction strategy for solving the proposed problem.

3- GCNs are usually used for classification, which makes it harder to benefit from its advantages in fMRI data processing for regression purpose.

1-4 Thesis Innovation

1- Using GCN model for gaining advantage of the functional connectivity information provided by available fMRI data in predicting brain age.

2- Using regions of interest (ROI) masks shared by different brain atlases to be applied on the resting-state fMRI data for acquiring the active regions of grayordinates related to our study and trying to ensemble the results derived using different atlases.

Chapter 2

Basic Concepts

2-1 Introduction

In this chapter, we will cover some review concepts for clarifying some terms that are involved in our study. We will explain brain fMRI and brain age related concepts. We will also disclose used prediction models concepts.

2-2 Brain Structure

The brain is considered the “control unit” of our bodies. It is considered to be the main organ in the central nervous system. It consists of 60% fats with the remaining constituents being water, protein, carbohydrates and salts (Chang, Ke and Chen, 2009). The brain contains Blood vessels and nerves as it is not a muscle itself. It has three main parts: the brain stem which connects it to the spinal cord, the cerebellum that controls regulating movement, motor learning, and maintaining equilibrium, and the cerebrum that houses the cerebral cortex (having the left and right hemispheres) and other small structures that manage conscious thought, decision-making, memory and learning processes, communication, and perception of external and internal stimuli. The grey matter and white matter consist the central nervous system, as the grey matter contains the majority of neuron cell bodies and other neural components. In the brain, the grey matter is a thin layer surrounding the cerebellum named “the cortex” (cerebral cortex and cerebellar cortex) whereas white matter is found in deeper tissues (Mercadante and Tadi, 2022).

2-3 Brain Age

Brain aging is unavoidable, but it occurs differently among different people. The development of the brain starts by the third week of gestation so that by the age of 6, the human brain forms 90% of its adult volume (Stiles and Jernigan, 2010). However, the frontal lobes responsible for executive functions may keep developing till the age of 35 (Johnson, Blum and Giedd, 2009). As a person ages, different body systems -including the brain- begin diminishing. Older people often face common normal memory changes; that is not related to Alzheimer's and other dementias. These common normal memory changes include difficulties in different episodic memory tasks including committing new information, recalling names and numbers, life events and other personal experiences (Nilsson, 2003). Brain aging causes different changes such as changes in the brain mass, ventriculomegaly, cortical thinning, white matter hyperintensities, synaptic pruning, axon myelination, morphological and functional connectivity and other physiological changes. The brain age is calculated by predicting age using brain imaging data. The difference between the chronological age and the predicted age is called the brain age gap (Cole *et al.*, 2019; Niu *et al.*, 2020).

2-4 Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI)

Neuroimaging techniques include different types; the most common types are MRI, fMRI, EEG, PET and CT scans. MRI and fMRI techniques share the same principles of atomic physics; however, MRIs allow examining the anatomical structure while the fMRIs allow examining the metabolic function or the brain activity. fMRI technique was developed in the early 1990s and has since become a very popular neuroimaging method while being considered to have some limitations due to the brain's circuitry and functional organization (Logothetis, 2008). In its short history, fMRI research has been plagued by issues like small sample sizes, the use of methods that lead to high number of false positives, and a small proportion of study results that have been independently reproduced. As the field has become more aware of these problems, many researchers have begun to adjust their approach to address them.

The human body is made of more than 50 percent of water. Each water molecule in the body contains two hydrogen atoms; these hydrogen atoms contain a proton. Protons have magnetic properties; when a magnet is present, they interact with the magnetic field. MRI and fMRI scanners use magnets to measure a signal from protons in the body. Thus, fMRI involves exposing the brain to multiple magnetic fields, and relies on the observation that protons in the nuclei of hydrogen atoms respond to this procedure by emitting an electromagnetic signal that can be detected by the fMRI scanner. The fMRI scanner is capable of determining some of the properties of the tissue the signal came from, and can use this information to reconstruct a high-resolution image of the brain.

Brain cells need oxygen to function; this is transported through the body via red blood cells in the blood on demand. Blood has magnetic properties that change depending on how much oxygen it contains. When there is a change in the oxygen level, the magnetic field around the blood vessel changes slightly which affects the protons close to the blood vessel in a way that the fMRI scanner can detect differences in the magnetic properties of oxygenated and deoxygenated blood, and thus can identify changes in the levels of oxygenated blood in different regions of the brain using a method called blood-oxygen-level-dependent, or BOLD, contrast. BOLD is typically what enables us to identify which brain areas are most active in fMRI. Areas of the brain that are more active tend to receive higher levels of oxygenated blood; hence, higher levels of oxygenated blood in a particular brain region are believed to correspond to higher neural activity in that region. On a typical fMRI image, color-coding is used to represent differences in the level of oxygenated blood and thus differences in activity. Activity in those areas can then be associated with whatever task was performed at the time of the scan. Lots of images of the brain are taken very quickly then processed on the computer to create a map showing how brain activity changes when the brain is doing different things. (Buxton, 2013)

2-5 Functional Connectivity

Functional connectivity is defined as the temporal correlation between remote neurophysiological events so that if two parts of the brain have a signal that increase or decrease together, we can call them functionally connected. For measuring functional

connectivity, there exist three approaches including seed-based correlation, independent component analysis (ICA) (Joel *et al.*, 2011) and graph theory (Wang, Zuo and He, 2010). Seed-based correlation focuses on picking a particular seed region of interest and take its timeseries to have its correlation with other brain voxels calculated to obtain a correlation map (connectivity map). It can be written as the following formula:

$$C_{SB}(x_1, x_2) = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T S(x_1, t)S(x_2, t)}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T S^2(x_1, t)} \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T S^2(x_2, t)}}$$

Where $s(x,t)$ is the BOLD signal of voxel x at time t given T time points.

Independent component analysis focuses on getting the time series of different voxels to be decomposed into different spatial components that share a particular characteristic time course. It can be described using the formula:

$$S(x, t) = \sum_{k=1}^K M_k(x)A_k(t)$$

Where M_k is the spatial map and A_k is the time course of component k over K independent components.

The graph theory focuses on taking regions of interest that can be either a partition of the entire brain or just a subset of some of the regions in the brain and then calculating all the possible pairwise correlations between the regions.

The same functional connectivity appears at rest state. So, in addition to task-related neural activity, there is spontaneous neural activity that co-activates within these different networks. These also produce BOLD responses that we can detect with MRI.

The first resting-state study was done by *B. Biswal et al* in 1995 (Biswal *et al.*, 1995). He had individuals performing a bilateral finger tapping task to get the corresponding activation images of that task to be compared with the correlations in motor cortex taken at rest. The result proved the similarity between the correlations taken at rest with the actual activation map obtained during the task. *Figure 1* shows ten different networks that are consistently observed across individuals (Smith *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 1 Ten well-matched network pairs that were paired using ICA spatial cross-correlation on a 36-subject resting fMRI dataset

2-6 Brain Atlases

The brain is a very complex system. Therefore, to study its functions and investigate treatments for neurological diseases, researchers needed an atlas that was later able to enhance automated image analysis. An atlas describes the brain volumetric or surface geometry. Brain atlases define neuroanatomical coordinates labeled according to a scheme (Evans *et al.*, 2012). In 1909, Korbinian Brodmann used cell staining on human and monkey brains to identify the organization of the mammalian cortex. According to brain cell organization, or “cytoarchitecture” the cortex is divided into 52 regions known as “Brodmann areas”. In 1957, Jean Talairach and his colleagues published their first stereotactic atlas that helped in developing the known Talairach atlas in the 1988 edition. In 1950s, Schaltenbrand Atlas was produced to be later updated in 1977. In 1994, MNI305 Atlas was created by the Montreal Neurological Institute after acquiring 305 subjects’ MRIs, which formed the initial version of “MNI space”. In 2001, the ICBM project collected 450 healthy brain MRIs and linearly registered 152 subjects to the MNI305 Atlas.

The ICBM Atlas was then created with many advantages over the MNI305 Atlas. In 2003, the ICBM152 Atlas was updated using nonlinear registration.

2-6-1 Yeo 2011 Atlas

In 2011, Yeo Atlas used registered 1000 subject resting-state fMRI dataset with surface-based alignment. For the parcellation of functional-based coupled regions, clustering approach was applied that resulted in getting each hemisphere divided into 7 (*figure 2*) or

17 (*figure 3*) functionality region across the cerebral cortex projected into MNI152 space for studying intrinsic functional connectivity (Thomas Yeo *et al.*, 2011).

2-6-2 Multi-Modal Parcellation (MMP)

In 2016, Glasser *et al.* created a multi modal parcellation that partitions the cortex hemispheres into 180 cortical regions each, that were based on changes in different properties corresponding to the cortical areas constructing the HCP-MMP atlas. The connectivity studied for this parcellation purpose included functional and structural connections. For each parcel, BOLD time courses were averaged across all region grayordinates. Functional connectivity matrix with $N \times N$ shape was then calculated using Pearson correlation between each two pairs of parcels and averaging the correlations across all subjects. The parcellation was few years later expanded to 379 regions by adding 19 standard subcortical structures from the FreeSurfer average atlas and grouped using their function and interconnectivity. It was also called the augmented HCP atlas (Glasser *et al.*, 2016; Doyen *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 4 180 regions identified for the hemispheres according to the multi-modal parcellation (MMP) with their areal assignments

2-6-3 Cole-Anticevic Brain-wide Network Partition

In 2019, The Cole-Anticevic Brain-wide Network Partition was released. It used MMP original 180 parcels/hemisphere cortical parcellation and extended it by a 358 parcellation of subcortical regions to form a whole-brain parcellation. Although being more exposed to being noisy, it was proved to be symmetric and replicable solution (Ji *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 5 cortical-subcortical parcellations using Cole-Anticevic Brain-wide Network Partition

2-7 Machine Learning

Machine Learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Artificial Intelligence is a technique that enables the machine to mimic human behavior. Machine Learning is a technique to achieve AI through algorithms trained with data. To learn and improve through experience is the human behavior Artificial Intelligence enables for machines. Machine Learning brings together statistics and computer science to enable computers to learn how to do a given task without being programmed to do so, similar to a human brain that uses experience to improve a certain task. A learning machine will seek statistical patterns within the data -without the help of the programmer- that will enable it to recognize a certain target in the input data. The main types of Machine Learning are supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning is the learning based on the associations between features and labels of a training data that enables the machine to predict the labels of future data using their features. Unsupervised Learning is the process of learning to cluster a training data with different features without labels to learn features association for unlabeled purpose (clustering). Reinforcement

Learning on the other hand is a reward-based learning working on the principle of feedback to evaluate its action and set a probability for such future occurrence. (Jordan and Mitchell, 2015)

2-8 Deep Learning

Deep Learning is a type of Machine Learning inspired by the structure of the human brain. In Machine Learning, the features that are used for reaching the target are provided directly, whereas in Deep Learning the features are picked out by the neural network without human intervention. Different Neural Networks work on different tasks as, for example, Deep Convolutional Networks deal with structured data, whereas Recurrent Neural Networks deal with sequential data. (Lecun, Bengio and Hinton, 2015).

There exist many deep architectures dealing with different data types.

2-8-1 Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a commonly used type of neural network used for problems where the input has an inherent two-dimensional structure like an image or any data with spatial dependencies. Like all neural networks, CNNs are made of layers that allow passing the information between them, however, characterized by having a convolution layer. Convolution is a filtering operation applied to the data to detect certain features. A data subject is considered to be a matrix of numbers, so a smaller filter matrix - called the kernel- is used to perform an element-wise product between the kernel and the portion of the subject matrix for checking the presence of certain feature in this portion. The results are summed-up to get a single value representing the existence of the feature. The kernel is then shifted by a number of digits to cover the next portion and so on, until the whole subject data matrix has been covered. The final result is a new matrix -called feature map- whose numbers describe where the target feature was found. A convolutional layer implements a number of kernels, each detecting a certain feature. Kernels do not need to be designed in advance; during training, the network decides which are the important features and adapts the kernel to detect them. (Aloysius and Geetha, 2018)

2-8-2 Graph Convolutional Networks

The Graph Convolutional Network or GCN is to take graph data which is $G(V, E)$ -with V is a set of vertices and E is a set of edges- and to work with these vertices according to some node label. The goal of GCN is to encode graph structure and the features of nodes into low dimensional representation and to morph and modify these representations such that they can fit these node labels.

So, the input is considered to be the graph that is sequentially processed through hidden layers which are intermediate feature representation of a neural network. Eventually, these representations are flattened out into a soft matte probability distribution over labels.

The high level of GCN and why it is called graph convolution network is this idea of convolution that is applied as in CNNs. However, in image data convolution -having a fixed structure - a convolution aggregates the features of local pixels sequentially reducing the spatial dimension by clustering the features of nearby pixels. GCN on the other hand can use spectral and spatial methods for work on structured graphs.

Spatial graphs include nodes with local spatial features, that this GCN would combine these features using an aggregation operation with local filters to be transformed to higher-order features. An aggregator collects the information from neighborhood nodes and summarizes them to be then fused with the information to get the new representation of the node for the final prediction. Aggregation is done according to the function

$$H^{l+1} = f(H^l, A),$$

Where H^l is the set of features representation of all nodes on layer l , A is the adjacency matrix (can be weighted) and f is the chosen non-linear function.

As an example, for a vertex v_i , over certain layer, its node corresponding features are defined as

$$\bar{h}_i = \sum_{j \in N_i} u_{ij} h_j,$$

Where $H = [h_1, h_2, \dots]$ are the node's corresponding features, N_i are the vertex's neighbors'

feature vectors and u_{ij} is the weight of the edge connecting v_i and v_j .

On the other hand, the information transformation is applied according to the function

$$L(\bar{H}, W) = F(W\bar{H} + b),$$

Where L is the transformation learning algorithm, \bar{H} is the intermediate representation, F is the activation function and $W \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{in} \times d_{out}}$ and $b \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{out}}$ are the trainable weight matrix and the trainable bias vector, respectively (Danel *et al.*, 2020).

Spectral domain convolution is defined by applying eigen decomposition of the adjacency or Laplacian matrix on the graph for understanding graph connectivity representation. This allows the recognition of clusters or sub-graphs in the given graph using Fourier space.

Chapter 3:

Literature Review

3-1 Introduction

There is a large variety of provided methods by previous researches that target the prediction of brain-age. Brain scans are often the most used for this purpose, with having deep learning as the great performance algorithms being focused on segmentation and classification of reconstructed brain scans images. On the other hand, Graph convolution networks are widely studied for different approaches using neuroimaging.

In this chapter, we are going to discuss relevant literature regarding the different methods used for the research problem and our used methods as presented for different approaches. The goal of investigating the mentioned literature is to provide an overview of the most effective algorithms and learn how well they can be implemented in similar applications.

3-2 Brain Age Prediction Literature

There exists a number of literatures regarding the prediction of brain age problem, either on solving the problem as a whole or on solving specific detailed parameters and problem methods affecting the prediction results. In this section we elaborate on the recent years of work on the brain age prediction problem. Note that GCN has, at the moment of writing, not yet been applied to the target problem in published literature. Nevertheless, this section

is included to develop a good understanding of the other methods that already have been applied and to learn about their usage and results.

3-2-1 MRI Based Studies for Brain Age Prediction

A prevalent brain age prediction research track is one that uses MRIs for solving the problem. Among older studies, the work of (Aycheh *et al.*, 2018) introduces a model for brain age prediction using cortical thickness data of large cohort brain images. The MRIs of final 2705 normal subjects (age:45-91) were derived from the Health Promotion Center of Samsung Medical Center (SMC) and parcellated into 148 regions using the Destrieux Atlas. They were concerned about improving the accuracy of brain age prediction by combining the most important features selection model chosen to be Sparse Group Lasso (SGL) regularization model with the prediction model fitted using a kernel method chosen to be Gaussian Process Regression (GPR). The best results considering the proposed model and the acquired dataset was Root-mean-square deviation (RMSE) = 5.18 years and mean absolute error (MAE) = 4.08 years. The models were trained using 10-fold cross-validation repeated 10 times for reliability of the performance results.

The work by (Sone *et al.*, 2019) describes a brain age prediction model for the other purpose of relating it and evaluating different types of epilepsy. Regarding their brain age prediction model, it used a standard nu-support vector regression (nu-SVR) with principal component analysis for overfitting reduction and overcoming the curse of dimensionality and applied it on 1196 healthy control subject and 318 patients with epilepsy. The healthy controls aged between 20 and 89 years, and the 10-fold cross validation conducted on them with the proposed regression model resulted in an MAE of 5.28 years and a correlation value (r) = 0.9.

Differently, a deep learning method to solve the brain age problem is introduced as published by (Jonsson *et al.*, 2019). In their work, they focus on the prediction using 3D-CNN ResNet. The method was trained independently for each image type, then the four predictions were combined using a majority voting scheme method and a linear regression blending method. This was compared to other methods using feature extraction and

machine learning. The model was applied on structural brain MRIs for 4456 healthy Icelanders (1264 MRI used several times after being augmented to acquire larger dataset for deep learning training). It was also evaluated on the IXI and UK Biobank datasets. All ages range between 45 and 80 years. The obtained results were MAE=3.39 and R2=0.87 on test data, MAE=4.149 and R2=0.907 for IXI dataset and MAE=3.631 and R2=0.614 for UK Biobank dataset.

The work proposed by (Treder *et al.*, 2021a) proposes an analysis studying the correlation between the chronological age and the brain age delta (or brain age gap derived by calculating the absolute difference between the chronological age and the predicted brain age of a subject). The results of this analysis were used as constraints for the regression models. The brain age models used for regression were Linear, Ridge, and Kernel Ridge regression. MRI scans of total 3300 subjects were used for training and validation. Kernel Ridge regression was the best to deliver the least MAE scores (5.16 using Unconstrained and correlation=0.3).

Concurrently, (Peng *et al.*, 2021) presented a 3D CNN, Simple Fully Convolutional Network (SFCN) model, for predicting brain age and sex classification. The model was applied on T1 MRI data of 14,503 subjects (age: 44-80 years) that were acquired from the UK Biobank dataset. The model's performance was very notable as it achieved an MAE score of 2.14y considering the brain age prediction, and an accuracy of 99.5% considering the sex classification.

Recent in article (Han *et al.*, 2022) the authors compare the performance of various machine learning models in predicting brain age using brain morphometric data. They found that certain models, such as random forests and gradient boosting, performed better than others, such as linear regression and support vector machines. The authors also discuss the potential applications of accurate brain age prediction, including the ability to identify individuals at risk for age-related brain disorders and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions designed to slow brain aging. Selected models being applied on 1113 MRI from the HCP dataset, MAE ranged between 2.75 and 3.12, while being applied on 601 MRI from the Cam-CAN dataset resulted in MAE range between 7.08 and 10.50 and

applying them on 567 MRI from Information eXtraction from Images (IXI) dataset resulted in MAE between 8.04 and 9.86.

3-2-2 fMRI Based Studies for Brain Age Prediction

Some alternatives to MRI-based predicting models used fMRI datasets to predict the brain age by taking an advantage of the metabolic function that measures brain activity and detects changes in it. Among the earlier studies to take on this path, (Li, Satterthwaite and Fan, 2018b) developed a CNN model to use fMRIs' fine-grained whole brain FC measures for better brain age prediction. The calculated voxel-wise whole brain FC measures were stacked as multi-channel 4D FC images input to the built deep CNNs. The innovation in the method itself is the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to analyze functional connectivity patterns in the brain. CNNs are a type of deep learning algorithm that are commonly used in image and speech recognition, but they have not been widely used in the analysis of functional brain imaging data. By using CNNs to analyze functional connectivity patterns, the method is able to identify complex and non-linear relationships between different regions of the brain that may be associated with brain age. This is a novel approach that has the potential to improve our understanding of brain aging and could be used for early detection and monitoring of age-related changes in the brain. The model was applied over 983 subjects' rs-fMRI derived from the PNC dataset (ages: 8 to 22). The obtained MAE was 2.15 ± 1.54 that showed significant improvement in the prediction compared to other traditional machine learning-based models that used the same dataset.

Then, the work done by (Zhai and Li, 2019) targeted using network-based principal component analysis (PCA) for extracting meaningful components from the fMRIs' FC matrices. The study used a machine learning algorithm to analyze the spatial and temporal features of the brain's functional networks, which are the interconnected regions of the brain that work together to perform specific functions. OLS, SVR, and Lasso regression models were used for the brain age prediction. 703 total subjects' scans from the Nathan Kline Institute—Rockland Sample (NKI-RS) dataset (ages: 4-85 years) and the Enhanced Nathan Kline Institute—Rockland Sample (NKI-RS-E) dataset (ages: 6-85 years) were

used for the study. Best MAE results were obtained using Lasso regression applied on network-based method (MAE=6.5 and $r=0.91$ as the 10-fold cross-validation scores, and MAE=8.8 and $r=0.838$ as the external validation scores).

In (Monti *et al.*, 2020), the work focuses on employing linear latent variable models for improving interpretability and predictive performance. For this, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), independent component analysis (ICA), Modular Hierarchical Analysis (MHA) and Modular Connectivity Factorization (MCF) models were experimented. The choosing of a regression model was limited to the usage of the simplest forms of linear regression model, in the interest of interpretability. The model was applied on different fMRI datasets: CamCAN (647 subjects, ages: 18-88 years), HCP (80 subjects, ages: 22-37 years) and ATR (191 subjects, ages: 20-70 years). For each dataset, the MHA latent variable model was the best to reach the minimum MAE score (approx. CamCAN MAE range = [8.5, 8.8], approx. HCP MAE range = [8.5, 10], approx. ATR MAE range = [6.5,10.5]).

A study by (Cole, 2020) investigated the performance of different single MRI modalities and the multimodality trained using Lasso regression model. T1-weighted MRI, T2-FLAIR, T2*, rs-fMRI, task fMRI, and diffusion-MRI are the modalities used through the study. The research was conducted on 2725 participant for the training and 14701 participants for the testing; all derived from the UK Biobank dataset. This study showed the outperformance of the multimodality approach followed by T1-weighted and diffusion-MRI phenotypes as the single modalities with best performance and correlation to the brain-age. The negative impact of biomedical and lifestyle factors was also studied through the research.

By the date of writing this work, the latest research done concerning the prediction of brain age using fMRI data was conducted by (Lund *et al.*, 2022). This study applied The Shrinkage Estimation of Regression Coefficients (slm) on the functional connectivity of rs-fMRI data (1126 subjects for training derived from the PNC dataset and 1387 subjects for testing derived from the HBN dataset). The proposed model achieved a correlation $r=0.6$, MAE=2.43 years and root mean square error (RMSE)=2.93 years for the 10-fold cross-validation on the PNC dataset. The independent test set on the HBN dataset showed results

of $r=0.54$, $MAE=4.24$ years and $RMSE=4.79$ years. Other independent testing examination were also applied on other datasets for further investigation of scanning site effects. Important connections between different brain regions for modeling brain age were also identified in the study; included regions were sensorimotor, visual, insular, DMN, cerebellar and language processing.

3-2-3 FMRI-Related Graph Convolutional Network Studies

Lately, (Gadgil *et al.*, 2020) paper introduced a spatio-temporal graph convolutional network (ST-GCN)-based framework for fMRI analysis and tested through predicting ages and genders of the involved subjects. The graphs constructed through this method define each node as a region on a specific timepoint. Nodes through temporal graphs have connections where edges connect a node of ROI with another node of the same ROI but a proceeding timepoint. However, nodes through spatial graphs have connections where edges connect a node of ROI with another node of different ROI but the same timepoint; weighted according to the relative correlation-based functional connectivity. Three ST-GC units compose the proposed ST-GCN model. The data used constituted of 773 rs-fMRI scans from the NCANDA dataset (ages 12–21 years) and 1096 rs-fMRI scans from the Human connectome project 1200 (HCP 1200) dataset (ages 22–35 years). The data was parcellated to 34 ROIs according to the Mindboggle-101 dataset. With 5-fold cross-validation, applied on NCANDA dataset, the prediction accuracies of ST-GCN with respect to age and sex were 77.7% and 79.8%, respectively, while applied on HCP for the purpose of sex prediction only, it achieved the highest accuracy of 83.7%. The obtained results were better than the results of proposed LSTM and GC-LSTM methods for comparison.

As for the purpose of age development using GCN, another study by (Li *et al.*, 2022) introduced a Graph Convolutional Network model for infant (6 to 811 days of age) brain age prediction. The model was applied on the resting-state fMRI data; as the functional connectivity derived from it was used for the graph construction. Each graph is an edge-based graph that corresponds to a subject, where a node is a brain regions and edges

between nodes are the derived functional connectivity. The proposed model achieved an MAE = 49.9 for infants with age more than 70 days.

Graph Convolution Networks were also applied on fMRI data for different objectives. (Zhao *et al.*, 2019) proposed a graph convolutional network-based method for mild cognitive impairment prediction. The graphs used for this study were built as population graphs (each node represents a subject and the edges represent the similarity between them according to the non-imaging features). The features represented for each subject node contains the upper half matrix of its relative functional connectivity derived from the parcellated (using AAL brain atlas) fMRI data. Ordinary GCN and Chebyshev's GCN (Cheby-GCN) were used and compared against other methods (ridge, random forest and multilayer perceptron). Three binary classifications were performed: early mild cognitive impairment (EMCI) vs. normal control (NC), late mild cognitive impairment (LMCI) vs. NC and EMCI vs LMCI. The proposed methods (especially for Cheby-GCN) had the best accuracy among all the classifications (78.4%, 84.3%, and 85.6%, respectively). Other research paper proposed for the same objective using dynamic spectral GCNs (DS-GCN) was (Xing *et al.*, 2019), however, each graph in this model corresponds to a single subject's fMRI data: nodes represent the anatomical ROI features and edges represent the graph nodes connectivity derived from the fMRIs' calculated functional connectivity. A spectral graph convolution-based LSTM (GC-LSTM) follows the graph construction for the corresponding prediction of status, gender, and age of each patient, which, in turn, was considered as assistant task training used for the final diagnosis. The model was applied on 294 training and 74 testing subjects derived from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative II (ADNI2) dataset. Compared to other methods that use static functional connectivity, dynamic connectivity-based model achieved better results as it obtained an accuracy of 79.7%, sensitivity of 86.5% and specificity of 73.0%. Another later proposed method by (Song *et al.*, 2021) for predicting significant memory concern (SMC) and mild cognitive impairment (MCI) suggested the usage of similarity-aware adaptive calibrated GCN (SAC-GCN) that works by, first, building two independent population graphs as nodes represent the subjects and edges represent their connections defined as the similarity-aware receptive fields which determine the similarity of the disease status between training subject (testing subjects are

simply connected to all existing subject) and weighted according to the gender, the equipment type and the computed correlation coefficient of feature vectors that these weights are updated according to random forest-based adaptive mechanism (one graph using fMRI information and the other using DTI information). The model proposed achieved a very remarkable mean classification accuracy of 86.83% after being applied on 170 subjects from the ADNI database having their fMRI and DTI data parcellated according to the AAL atlas to obtain 90 ROI; each leading to a 90×90 network.

Considering the prediction of Major Depressive Disorder using GCN models applied on resting state-fMRI, (Yao *et al.*, 2020) proposed a Temporal-Adaptive GCN (TAGCN) method that is applied by creating an adaptive graph convolutional layer with a temporal convolutional layer. Adaptive graph convolutional layer is where a graph is considered for each subject resembling the regions as nodes and linking them by combining Pearson's correlation coefficient of the functional connectivity, data driven matrix for different topology information between different time-series blocks and the topology information of brain functional connectivity in each time-series block. Temporal graph convolutional layer is where graph convolution is applied for processing sequential data derived as the output of the adaptive graph convolutional layer. Being applied to 533 subjects from an open-source MDD dataset, it acquired the highest accuracy of 0.738 ± 0.048 surpassing other comparison methods (SVM, CC+SVM, sGCN and GAN). For the same approach, (Kong *et al.*, 2021) discusses the use of a spatio-temporal graph convolutional network (ST-GCN) to predict the diagnosis and treatment response for individuals with major depressive disorder based on functional connectivity data derived from fMRI. The STGCN model includes modules for spatial graph attention convolution (SGAC) and temporal fusion, which are designed to improve the model's ability to learn features from the data and capture dynamic changes in functional connectivity over time. The model also includes a module for dimension reduction using a hierarchical brain parcellation. Applied on 82 MDD patients and 50 controls, The diagnosis accuracies are 84.14 and 83.93% across the study sites and the accuracy of treatment response prediction is as high as 89.63%.

The (Anirudh and Thiagarajan, 2019) research paper proposes a graph convolutional neural networks (GCNNs) method for classifying individuals with autism spectrum disorder

(ASD). The authors suggest that their approach, which involves "bootstrapping" the training process by starting with a small number of labeled examples and iteratively adding more, can improve the accuracy of ASD classification compared to traditional machine learning methods. A population graph-based approach is used through the research, where the weights assigned to the edges of the graph represent the similarity between the connectivity features of two different regions of interest (ROIs) in a particular subject, as measured using either the Euclidean dot product or a linear kernel. The method includes randomized ensemble of population graphs. The paper also discusses the results of an experimental study in which the proposed method was tested on a resting state fMRI data (rs-fMRI) for 1112 individuals with and without ASD from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset parcellated using Harvard-Oxford (HO) atlas. Compared to previous research papers using linear SVM and G-CNN, the proposed method was reported to have the highest accuracy. Likewise, (Rakhimberdina and Murata, 2020) addressed the solving the ASD classification problem along with the classification of Schizophrenia and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). fMRI data derived from ABIDE, COBRE and ADHD-200 databases were used through the study to have the responding functional connectivity describe the node features through the constructed population graph. The weights of edges between nodes are calculated based on Hamming distance between the subjects' phenotypic features. A simple linear graph convolutional model is applied to the obtained population graph, leading in comparison with other methods (ChebyGCN, GCN, Graph no features, Graph random and Graph identity) to higher accuracy for the three classifications (ABIDE: $68.56 \pm 4.33\%$, COBRE: $80.55 \pm 10.88\%$, ADHD-200: $74.35 \pm 4.76\%$). Another study proposed in (Yao *et al.*, 2021) uses a Mutual Multi-Scale Triplet Graph Convolutional Network (MMTGCN) that is a machine learning model that can -based on functional or structural connectivity- classify brain disorders tested for ADHD derived data from ADHD-200 dataset, Cerebral Small Vessel Disease (cSVD) derived data from WMH dataset and Alzheimer's Disease (AD) derived from ADNI dataset. This model uses graph convolutional networks (GCN) to analyze connectivity patterns in the brain and apply a triplet loss function to optimize the classification. The model is designed to operate at multiple scales, allowing it to capture both local and global connectivity patterns. It is also "mutual," meaning that it takes into

account both the connectivity patterns within individual brain regions and the relationships between brain regions. This model has the potential to improve diagnosis and treatment of brain disorders by providing a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of brain connectivity. However, a study was lately proposed in (Zhao *et al.*, 2022) presents a dynamic graph convolutional neural network (dGCN) framework was used to study connectome dysfunctions in ADHD. The dGCN framework allows for the analysis of connectivity patterns in the brain over time and can identify changes in connectivity that may be associated with ADHD. The dGCN framework has the potential to improve our understanding of ADHD and other brain disorders by providing a more dynamic and comprehensive view of brain connectivity. The graphs correspond each to a subject (resembling a network of ROI), with dynamic adjacency matrices calculated based on the k top Euclidean distance of the features of nodes. The method was compared to other methods including SVM, logistic regression, MLP, GCN and GAT. The proposed and comparing methods were applied to fMRI data of 635 subject derived from the ADHD-200 database to show that the proposed method had the best results (accuracy 72%, specificity 71.6% and sensitivity 72.2%). Nevertheless, among the latest articles that proposed a GCN-based method for brain disease classification was (Jiang *et al.*, 2020) that proposes the "Hi-GCN" that is a model designed to learn embeddings (representations) of brain networks and predict brain disorders (tested for Alzheimer's disease and autism spectrum disorder). The model is based on population graph convolutional network. The "Hi" in the name refers to the fact that the model has a hierarchical structure, with multiple layers of GCNs working together to learn more complex and nuanced embeddings. After being applied on 866 subjects' fMRI of ABIDE dataset, the model obtained an accuracy of 73.1% and an AUC of 82.3%, and applying it to 133 fMRI data from the ADNI dataset obtained an accuracy of 78.5% as well as AUC of 86.5%.

Among all previous studies, only (Li *et al.*, 2022) article that targeted infants' age prediction (was mentioned previously) and (Qu *et al.*, 2021) article that targeted cognitive ability prediction were the articles that used GCN-based models for a regression purpose. Regarding (Qu *et al.*, 2021), the model is trained on multi-modal data where for each modality a graph represents a single subject with nodes corresponding to the ROIs and

edges corresponding to the FC between them. The model is also regularized using a technique called manifold regularization, which helps to prevent overfitting and improve the generalization of the model. The EMR-MGCN is evaluated on a cognitive ability prediction task and is shown to outperform several baseline models.

3-3 Conclusion

We inspected different articles in this chapter: A summary table for different studies using fMRI data for brain age prediction is shown in *table 1*. For comparison, we checked articles that use fMRI for brain age prediction but found no article with significant results that uses the same HCP dataset's fMRI data. For investigating the advantages and strategies of using GCN-based models for fMRI data related analysis, we checked related articles to have their approaches applied for our brain age prediction goal in a similar manner.

Table 1 Models proposed for brain age prediction using fMRI data

Reference	Dataset	Subjects Number	Age Range (default in years)	Method	MAE
(Li, Satterthwaite and Fan, 2018b)	PNC	983	8 to 22	Deep CNN	2.15±1.54
(Zhai and Li, 2019)	NKI-RS, NKI-RS-E	703	4 to 85	OLS, SVR and Lasso	6.5 - 8.8
(Monti <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	CamCAN, HCP, ATR	647, 80, 191	19 to 88, 22 to 37, 20 to 70	OLS	[8.5, 8.8], [8.5, 10], [6.5,10.5]
(Cole, 2020)	UK Biobank	17461 (2725 subject among them for training)	45 to 80	Lasso	3.522
(Lund <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	PNC, HBN	1126, 1387	8 to 22	SLM	2.43 on PNC 4.24 on HBN
(Gadgil <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	NCANDA, HCP	773, 1096	12 to 21, 22 to 35	ST-GCN	Accuracy: 77.7% 79.8%
(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	infant fMRI scans	Unkown	6 to 811 days	BC-GCN-SE	49.9 days

According to the reviewed studies, we can see that the only published article that uses fMRI and GCN-based models for brain age prediction were (Gadgil *et al.*, 2020) and (Li *et*

al., 2022) that showed significant results. However, (Gadgil *et al.*, 2020) was dealing with the problem as a classification problem through predicting the age range the brain age belong to, and (Li *et al.*, 2022) addressed the infant brain age prediction which is different than predicting adults' brain age due to the manner of infants' growth. Still, GCN-based models have shown remarkable results for different brain diseases diagnosis and interpretation compared to other methods, so we are concerned about exploring the utilization of different GCN-based models for the prediction of brain age using fMRI.

Through previous studies we can also conclude that in general, the use of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to predict brain age and its association with psychiatric symptoms has some potential advantages and disadvantages.

Pros:

- 1- fMRI can provide a non-invasive way to measure brain activity, allowing for frequent and repeated measurements over time.
- 2- fMRI-based brain age prediction may allow for early identification of individuals at risk for psychiatric disorders.
- 3- Understanding the neural basis of brain age prediction may provide insight into the underlying causes of psychiatric disorders.

Cons:

- 1- fMRI is a complex technique and the results can be affected by many factors, such as head movement and scanner noise, which can reduce the accuracy of the predictions.
- 2- The relationship between brain age prediction and psychiatric symptoms is not well understood and further research is needed to confirm the findings.

The use of fMRI-based brain age prediction in clinical settings may raise ethical concerns, such as the potential for stigmatization or discrimination based on predicted brain age. As a further matter, there are several pros and cons to using graph convolutional networks (GCNs) for predicting brain age in contrast to other methods reviewed through the above literature.

Pros:

- 1- GCNs are well-suited for processing data that is organized as a graph, such as the connectivity patterns in brain networks.
- 2- GCNs can effectively capture both local and global features in the data, which is important for understanding the complex relationships in brain networks.
- 3- GCNs can be trained using large amounts of data, which is important for accurately predicting brain age.

Cons:

- 1- GCNs can be computationally expensive to train and use, which can be a problem for large-scale brain imaging studies.
- 2- GCNs can be sensitive to the choice of hyperparameters, which can make it difficult to optimize the model for a specific task.

GCNs may not be able to capture all of the relevant information in the data, which could lead to inaccurate predictions of brain age.

Chapter 4

Proposed Method

4-1 Introduction

As mentioned before, several methods were proposed to solve the brain age prediction issue by trying to acquire lower MAE scores as a main score for the majority of the studies. GCNs were also used and conveyed to be affecting for different fMRI studies. Therefore, as a new innovation, we are concerned about the usage of GCN models using different structures and strategies applied on parcellated resting-state fMRI data with different parcellations for predicting brain age. The proposed method is implemented in Python for data preprocessing and different GCN models buildings. In what follows, we will first introduce the data and how they are pre-processed, and the methods applied.

4-2 Dataset

Resting-state fMRI, demographic, and behavioral data were acquired from the WUMinn 1200 Human Connectome Project (HCP) data release. All the data were downloaded from the WU-Minn 1200 Human Connectome Project dataset release. HCP S1200 release comprised 1206 healthy young adults (age 22–35). There were 1094 subjects with both structural MRI and rs-fMRI. Both structural MRI and rs-fMRI were acquired on a customized Siemens 3T “Connectome Skyra” scanner at Washington University at St. Louis. The rs-fMRI was 2 mm isotropic with TR of 0.72s and 1200 frames per run (14.4 min). Each subject had two sessions of rs-fMRI, and each session contained two rs-fMRI runs (two LR and two RL rs-fMRI runs of total 4800 timepoints). Each scan is

preprocessed and saved as a CIFTI *.dtseries.nii file that contains resampled 91282 grayordinates (29696 left cortex vertices, 29716 right cortex vertices and 31870 subcortical voxels) over 1200 timepoint. We use nibabel python package to load the CIFTI file with the fMRI time series and extract the fMRI time series as a NumPy array. A sample fMRI plot at a specific time was shown in *figure 6*. Some images were found to be corrupted (some timepoints were missing) so they were excluded.

Figure 6 Sample subject (ID: 192641) plot at t=29 of the LR fMRI grayordinates timeseries

A number of behavioral and demographic measures were also collected by HCP. Subjects then having the imaging and non-imaging data were selected.

More details about the dataset can be found in (van Essen *et al.*, 2012, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013).

4-3 Data Preprocessing

For data normalizing/cleaning phase, incomplete data were removed (having less than 1200 timepoints or Nan values). For models utilizing non-imaging features chosen such that they are more correlating to the prediction of brain age according to the results provided by the supplementary material of (Sanford *et al.*, 2022), sex-specific predictions were performed, thus data of the two genders were separated, then among the obtained data, samples with complete non imaging data were selected.

FMRI data is afterward formatted by parcellating each scan using HCP-UTILS package containing predefined parcellations (Yeo7 and Yeo17 2011 atlas (Thomas Yeo *et al.*, 2011), Cole-Anticevic Brain-wide Network Partition (Ji *et al.*, 2019) and Glasser et.al. Multi-Modal Parcellation (Glasser *et al.*, 2016; Doyen *et al.*, 2022)). The parcellation is applied by extracting the target ROIs from the fMRI grayordinates timeseries, then the mean value of each group of grayordinates corresponding to certain region is calculated for assigning the region's mean value. Later formatting differs from models to another; most models stack the parcellated NumPy scans arrays and convert them to torch tensors for later processing through the model.

For getting the connectome matrix representing the functional connectivity between different regions, *nilearn.connectome.ConnectivityMeasure* was used with *kind="correlation"* to calculate the correlation of the given data. The *fit_transform* method first fits the data to the model and then transforms it into the matrices. It is used to produce the connectivity matrices that are needed for machine learning tasks such as classification and regression.

As for data scaling, we -in few models- tried to apply a threshold for the correlation values of the functional connectivity. Non-imaging features (demographic and behavioral data), in the models using them, were also combined to form a score (between 0.0 and 1.0) and the different values forming this score were scaled according to the output analysis in the supplemental tables of the article (Sanford *et al.*, 2022) that provides univariate associations of non-imaging predictors with brain age gap (that quantifies the difference between chronological age and age predicted by applying machine-learning). The important features

were chosen according to the same article and reorganized as the sample shown in *Table 1*. However, since the majority of important features that correspond to the brain age prediction of female subjects were not accessible at the time of the study, female subjects were excluded from the study.

Table 2 Extracted demographic and behavioral data for some selected sample subjects

Subject					
ID	age	gender	race	emot_supp	sleep_q
100206	27	0	White	43.9	6
100307	27	1	White	45	4
100408	33	0	White	50.1	4
100610	27	0	White	56.8	4
Black or African					
101006	35	1	Am.	62.5	2

4-4 Graphs Construction

A graph $G = (V, E, W)$ is described using a group of nodes or vertices (V), a group of edges connecting the nodes (E) and a group of weights (W) corresponding to the group of edges if the graph is weighted. In our work, we constructed two types of graphs: individual graphs and population graphs.

As shown in Figure 7, for individual graphs, each graph corresponds to a single subject where a node describes the information corresponding to a region. In some models, as in Figure 7(a), the node features are defined to be the array containing the functional connectivity scores between the node region and other regions. In other models, as in Figure 7(b), the node features are defined to be the complete timeseries values of the specified region over the 1200 timepoints, or the row through the identity matrix specifying the selected region. The weighted edges between nodes are the functional connectivity between the regions derived for each subject fMRI (using

nilearn.connectome.ConnectivityMeasure) or derived from the Group Average Functional Connectivity (available in the WU-Minn HCP dataset).

As shown in Figure 8, for population graphs, a graph corresponds to the whole dataset where a node describes a single subject fMRI information. In some models, Figure 8(a), the node information describes the functional connectivity matrix derived for the corresponding specific subject (the upper-triangle of the symmetric FC matrix is usually extracted, converted to a 1D array and used for this purpose). In other models, as in Figure 8(b), the node information describes the averaged value of the whole regions over the 1200 timepoints resulting in a 1D array of size that is equal to the number of regions. The weighted edges between nodes are the similarity scores computed between subjects according to their most influential non-imaging information available. However, the most influential non-imaging features for predicting females' brain age were not attainable, so models using non-imaging features were only applied for male subjects.

Figure 7 Preprocessing data for population-based model building

Figure 8 Preprocessing data for individual-based model building

4-5 Graph Convolutional Network Model for Predicting Brain Age

GCN is a type of neural network that is designed to operate on graph-structured data. In this type of network, the nodes of the graph are treated as the input and the edges between the nodes are used to propagate information. The graph convolutional layers of a GCN are responsible for performing these propagations by updating the representations of the nodes based on their local neighborhoods.

For taking advantage of the subjects' relationships or the fMRI data spatiotemporal information, a Graph convolutional network or GCN model is proposed for applying a convolution on the constructed graph that results in perceiving feature vectors to be passed through a neural network for training. The GCN model was built using GCNConv, DenseGCNConv and Linear layers imported from Pytorch and Pytorch geometric libraries. We used the rectified linear unit (ReLU) as the activation function as it is the most commonly used. This is because the ReLU activation function is computationally efficient and has been found to work well in practice for GCNs. We used L1Loss function imported from torch.nn module as the loss function for the training evaluation; this loss function calculates the mean absolute error (MAE) derived by calculating the absolute difference between the brain age prediction x and the chronological age target y corresponding to each subject, then, as it operates over all the subjects, their mean is calculated.

For the population graphs, as shown in *figure 9*, the whole graph of the complete selected subjects was considered as the input for the GCN model for training. After executing the proposed GCN model using the population-based graph, we obtained an array output of the predicted brain ages, where the second GCN layer produced a single neuron prediction for each node corresponding to a subject.

Figure 9 GCN model applied for population graphs

On the other hand, for the individual graphs, as shown in *figure 10*, each subject graph was considered as an input for the GCN model, and the model was trained for numerous epochs, each epoch looping over the subjects' graphs and training the GCN model using each graph sequentially. The second GCN layer produces a single neuron aggregation score that corresponds to the node region, then, the scores of the nodes are used as an input for the linear layer for getting a linear transformation of the input data resulting in the final

subject's brain age prediction. Predictions are then appended to form an array of predictions.

Figure 10 GCN model applied on individuals' graphs

Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) was imported from *torch* library and used as the models' optimizer with learning rate 0.01 and different number of epochs dependent on the size of the features corresponding to the parcellation applied each time (early stopping was used). Gradients computation and parameters update with those gradients is done through learning with MAE as the loss function.

4-6 Graph Convolutional Network Model Parameters and hyperparameters

In a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), parameters are weights and bias. These parameters are learned during the training process by minimizing the difference between the predicted output and the true output and are used to make predictions on new data with an optimized performance. The weights are used to determine how much influence each neighboring node has on the representation of a given node, while the biases are used to shift the overall output of the layer. The number and size of these parameters depend on the architecture of the GCN and the size of the input graph. For example, if the GCN has multiple convolutional layers, there will be more parameters than if it only has one. Also, the number of parameters will depend on the number of input and output features of each layer, the number of nodes in the graph, and the number of edges.

Concerning the bias and weights parameters, which are the most important parameters in GCN models, weights are initialized through the graph construction phase according to the calculated functional connectivity or according to the similarity between subjects (depending on the targeted graph structure); on the other hand, the biases in a GCN are a part of the model's parameters that can be trained and updated during the training process. The biases are used to shift the overall output of the graph convolutional layers, and they can be learned by the optimizer in order to minimize the difference between the predicted output and the true output. When training a GCN, the optimizer will update the weights and biases of the graph convolutional layers in order to minimize the loss function. The optimizer will iteratively adjust the values of the parameters based on the gradients of the loss function with respect to each parameter. Once the training process is complete, the final values of the biases can be used to make predictions on new data. It's also worth noting that, during the training process, the biases can also be initialized with zero or a small random number, and the optimizer will adjust them accordingly. The final values of these parameters can be used to make predictions on new data.

On the other hand, hyperparameters are settings that are set before training and control the overall behavior of the model training process. Hyperparameters considered in the GCN

models include the number of layers, the number of neurons in each layer, and the learning rate.

Considering the number of neurons in each layer, the size of the input layer is of course equal to the number of features in the input data and the size of the output layer is equal to 1 corresponding to the predicted age in the individual graphs, and equal to the number of subjects corresponding to the subjects' predicted ages in the population graphs. Determining the number of hidden nodes to use in a model was a challenging task. The number of hidden nodes depends the task itself, the size of the input data, and the architecture of the model. To determine the number of hidden nodes in our GCN models, we start with a small number of hidden neurons and increment the number until performance improves. The number of hidden neurons is considered to range from a small number, such as 32, to a large number, such as 2048. Different numbers of hidden neurons are tried and evaluate the performance of your model on a validation set. However, the size of the input data is taken into account as the number of input features changes using each parcellation, a larger input dataset might require more hidden nodes to capture the complexity of the data. The model's performance is monitored using MAE evaluation metric and corresponding scatterplot. Increasing the number of hidden neurons is stopped when there is no significant improvement in performance or if the model starts to overfit the training data. Determining the optimal number of hidden neurons is an iterative process that required experimentation.

Both hyperparameters and parameters play important roles in determining the performance of the GCN model, and optimizing both is important for obtaining the best results.

4-7 Predictions Ensemble

Using each parcellation, we were able to produce a set of predictions. To get final predictions, two ensemble methods (shown in figure 11) were used:

4-7-1 Ensemble by Aggregation

Ensemble by Aggregation involves training the instances each time using a different input data (derived using different parcellations), and then averaging their predictions. This approach can be used to reduce variance within noisy dataset-based predictions.

4-7-2 Ensemble by Regression

Ensemble by regression involves training the instances each time using a different input data (derived using different parcellations) and then combining their predictions by using a meta-model chosen to be Support Vector Regression (SVR). The idea behind ensemble by regression is to capture the complementarity of the base models and improve the overall performance of the ensemble. This approach can reduce the bias of the model and improve its generalization performance. Impacting the regression ensemble, subjects' corresponding non-imaging features were brought as features along with the different predictions for improving the final prediction corresponding to each subject.

Figure 11 Predictions Ensemble Methods

Chapter 5:

Results and Evaluation

5-1 Introduction

For brain age prediction, different brain imaging technologies were used through previous publications. The results of this study are evaluated according to the usage of resting state-fMRI data for brain age prediction. Results are relative to the fMRI data derived as a subset of the WU-Minn 1200 Human Connectome Project.

5-2 Evaluation Metrics

As for the general metrics used for the evaluation of regression problems, we used Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root of the Mean of the Square of Errors (RMSE) metrics for this purpose. However, the main metric used through our study for optimization and evaluation is MAE.

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is a commonly used metric for evaluating the performance of a regression model. MAE measures the average absolute difference between the predicted values and the true values. It is expressed in the same unit as the target variable and is less sensitive to outliers than Mean Squared Error (MSE).

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) is a commonly used metric for evaluating the performance of a model. It measures the difference between predicted and actual values and gives an idea of how "far off" the predictions are from the actual values. In simple words, it

is the square root of the average of the square of the differences between the predicted and actual values.

The formulas of above metrics are provided below:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

Where n is the number of samples, y_i is the true value of the i -th sample, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the i -th sample. Σ is the sum operator.

5-3 Evaluation of Population/GCN-based Models

As it was explained through chapter 4, for each method different predictions were acquired using single parcellations and by the two ensemble methods.

As we can recognize in *table 3*, the best MAE was obtained by the GCN-based model applied on a population graph with node features originated as the upper-triangle of the connectivity matrix corresponding to the fMRI of the node subject. However, as shown by Anscombe's quartet which is a set of four datasets created by statistician Francis Anscombe in 1973 that have nearly identical descriptive statistics, but vastly different distributions and appearances when graphed, visualizing data before analyzing it is considered to be a major importance; thus, we plotted the corresponding scatterplots representing the fitting of training sets with the predictions of testing sets to see which is shown to have better scatterplots. Such datasets as the one we have are considered highly vulnerable to face Anscombe's Quartet issue.

As shown in *figure 12*, the corresponding scatterplots of the models applied on population graphs were much more disperse and of small range predictions compared to the scatterplots of models applied on individual graphs, which show the ability for the later models to be more precise. The high variations of the results between different parcellations might be due to the high outliers' possibility of occurrence, and that is why in such problems the ensemble of different parcellations might help in reducing the possibility of being affected by the outliers.

Among models with individual-based graphs, the best scatterplots were acquired using nodes with corresponding regional full timeseries features, shown in *figure 13*.

Table 3 Obtained MAE and RMSE scores for the different GCN models we built corresponding to all parcellations and ensemble methods

	individualGCN features= full timeseries		individualGCN features= connectivity matrix		individualGCN features= region binary location		popGCN features= averaged timeseries		popGCN features= connectivity matrix	
	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE
YEO7_LR	3.79	4.6	3.29	3.89	3.06	3.69	2.96	3.59	4.71	6.04
YEO7_RL	3.03	3.5	3.04	3.76	3.03	3.67	2.9	3.52	4.6	5.96
YEO17_LR	3.92	4.7	3.25	3.91	3.03	3.68	2.91	3.52	2.94	3.55
YEO17_RL	2.92	3.54	3.45	4.13	3.08	3.69	2.9	3.53	3.07	3.66
MMP_LR	3.33	4.17	3.14	3.72	3.3	3.98	2.9	3.52	2.95	3.57
MMP_RL	3.05	3.61	3.51	4.16	3.39	4	2.9	3.52	2.84	3.48
CA_LR	3.22	4.01	3.06	3.64	3.21	3.85	2.91	3.52	2.87	3.5
CA_RL	3.11	3.78	3.53	4.26	3.98	4.54	2.9	3.52	4.52	5.33
AggEns	3.12	3.72	3.14	3.81	3.07	3.75	2.91	3.53	3.31	3.97
RegEns	3.11	3.77	3.02	3.68	3.08	3.79	2.92	3.55	2.88	3.55

Figure 12 Scatter plot (a) shows the chronological age compared to the predictions acquired using GCN model applied on a population graph with connectivity matrices initialized as the node features. Scatter plot (b) shows the chronological age compared to the predictions acquired using GCN model applied on individuals' graphs with the full timeseries of each region initialized as node features

Yeo-7	Yeo-17	MMP
CA	Aggregation Ensemble	Regression Ensemble

Figure 13 resulted scatterplots for Individuals graphs-based model using full timeseries as node features

5-4 Comparison with traditional machine learning methods

For comparison, we checked articles that uses fMRI for brain age prediction but found no article with significant results or with comparable “imaging modality-objective” settings that uses the same HCP dataset’s fMRI data, as mentioned through the conclusion of the literature review; so, we tested the usage of Lasso, Ridge, SVR and linear regression techniques using the same dataset of fMRIs. The chosen techniques are the same techniques used through previous literature, so we selected them. The models used the timeseries as the input and the chronological ages as the targets. Lasso regression showed simple averaging of the ages used in training, so no fitting of data was obtained. Ridge regression had different results (shown through *table 4* and *figure 14*) but was still weaker than the result obtained by the GCN-based models (especially models using individual graphs).

Table 4 Obtained MAE and RMSE scores for traditional machine learning models used through previous literatures corresponding to all parcellations and ensemble methods

	Ridge Regression		Lasso Regression		SVR		Linear Regression	
	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE
YEO7_LR	3.51	4.28	3.11	3.67	3.07	3.67	3.52	4.27
YEO7_RL	3.63	4.52	3.11	3.67	3.13	3.7	3.62	4.56
YEO17_LR	3.45	4.13	3.11	3.67	3.07	3.66	3.49	4.18
YEO17_RL	3.46	4.34	3.11	3.67	3.12	3.7	3.46	4.38
MMP_LR	3.16	3.72	3.11	3.67	3.08	3.67	3.2	3.75
MMP_RL	3.19	3.89	3.11	3.67	3.12	3.7	3.18	3.9
CA_LR	3.06	3.63	3.08	3.65	3.1	3.68	3.13	3.69
CA_RL	3.1	3.7	3.12	3.67	3.12	3.69	3.09	3.7
AggEns	3.15	3.76	3.11	3.67	3.1	3.68	3.14	3.78
RegEns	3.09	3.68	3.08	3.68	3.08	3.68	3.09	3.68

Figure 14 Scatter plot shows the chronological age compared to the predictions acquired using Ridge model after ensemble by regression

Among the mentioned studies that use Human Connectome Project for brain age prediction, we were able to obtain a relatively good promising results using an evident small number of rs-fMRI subjects. This can be viewed as an indication of the effectivity of using GCN models for rs-fMRI analysis for predicting brain age. The models we created were relatively easier to implement than other deep learning methods, considering the fixed number of effective GCN layers (two layers), and since no other layers are needed except for a final linear layer used to produce the final predictions from the second GCN layer outputs. Using multi-atlas approach was also effective for reducing some extreme outliers' prediction's residual errors and for taking benefit of different functional connectivity matrices resulting according to different parcellation criteria. It also provided an indication about the most effective parcellations for brain age prediction when needed to use a single atlas for faster modelling.

Chapter 6:

Conclusion and Future Work

In our proposed study, we reviewed previous work and concluded that GCN models were able to get important features representations of brain imaging and learn from them. Accordingly, we examined using GCN models for rs-fMRI population-based graphs (PGCN) and individual-based graphs (IGCN) using different parcellations and representations. Obtained experimental results give an idea that our proposed GCN-based models, especially IGCN, surpass traditional machine learning methods and can be promising through future work.

Due to our hardware restraint, we had to use part of the available fMRI in the HCP dataset for our study without being able to use the full dataset for the objective. However, this may be regarded as a sort of model compression, where a smaller, more effective model can use less data to perform at a similar level to a larger model built using other machine learning methods. As less data is needed for training, there may be cost savings, enhanced performance on edge devices, and other advantages including that a simpler model is easier to understand and comprehend which could also be seen as a sort of interpretability or comprehensibility.

Some non-imaging data were also inaccessible which might have affected the graph construction phase, leading to less precise performance.

Comparing to other studies using different datasets, brain imaging-based age prediction is also considered to be more challenging for subjects with small age ranges, such as young adults, than for subjects with larger age ranges, such as infants or older adults. One reason for this is that, compared to other developmental phases, such as infancy or aging, the brain changes less quickly throughout young adulthood. As a result, in young adults, it might be more challenging to spot minor variations in brain structure or function that are connected to age. Furthermore, because of factors like education, work, and lifestyle, young adults' brain development may vary considerably, making it more challenging to predict age from brain imaging data. On the other hand, age prediction for infants or older individuals using brain imaging may be easier because the brain changes more quickly during these developmental periods. For instance, during the first few years of life, the brain of an infant undergoes fast development and change, which can make it simpler to spot changes in brain structure or function that are connected to age. Similar to this, older persons' brains experience aging-related changes including hippocampal shrinkage, which can make it simpler to estimate age from brain imaging data. This topic concerning the bias was circumstantially discussed by (Treder *et al.*, 2021b).

Although the results of our method have been encouraging, there are still a number of areas where more research could enhance the algorithm's effectiveness. First, we can try more optimization for the proposed methods using different strategies to improve the model on particular image subcategories. This might result in even greater performance with certain dataset. Second, we can use more data for training them as training the model on a wider range of data might enhance its generalization skills. Finally, we can combine different imaging modalities (like the fMRI with structural MRI) for adjusting the graph constructions.

This work has demonstrated that GCN-based models can be successful for brain age prediction using fMRI, although there is still potential for development. The upcoming research, in our opinion, has the potential to considerably enhance the algorithms' performance and advance the field of brain age prediction.

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